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Flow diverting stent monotherapy as the best choice in the treatment of intracranial blood blister-like aneurysms: a systematic review

OBJECTIVE: To evaluate the effectiveness and safety of flow-diverting stent (FDS) monotherapy in the treatment of intracranial blood blister-like aneurysms (BBAs) through a detailed systematic review. **METHODS:** This review adheres to the PRISMA guidelines, focusing on studies utilizing FDS monotherapy for BBAs, spanning from July 2010 to November 2023. A systematic search across databases including Embase, Medline/PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar was conducted. Studies in English that solely used FDS for BBA treatment and assessed perioperative complications were included. Data from 23 studies encompassing 181 cases were systematically analyzed for patient demographics, aneurysm characteristics, treatment specifics, and outcomes. **RESULTS:** The collected data indicates a dominant occurrence of BBAs in the internal carotid artery (86.9%), with a mean patient age of 50.27 years and a higher prevalence in females (73.43%). Treatment timing varied, with 45.9% treated within the first three days, 35.7% were treated between 4 and 14 days, and 18.4% of patients were treated after 14 days. The study found a complete occlusion rate of 88.1% in follow-up imaging and a favorable clinical outcome in 82.2% of cases. Periprocedural complications were reported in 19.2% of patients, with a related mortality rate of 3.9%. **CONCLUSIONS:** The systematic review demonstrates that FDS monotherapy is highly effective and safe in the treatment of intracranial BBAs. It offers a high rate of complete aneurysm occlusion, favorable clinical outcomes, and low complication rates. These results highlight FDS monotherapy as a prominent treatment method, ensuring robust aneurysmal protection while maintaining the patency of the parent artery.

Keywords: Flow diverting stent monotherapy, Intracranial blood blister-like aneurysms

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